
THE INFLUENCE OF INQUIRY LEARNING MODEL AND LEARNING MOTIVATION ON RESULTS LEARNING HISTORY AT STATE 6 HIGH SCHOOL BANDAR LAMPUNG

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Abstract:

To assist a solution to the problem of the test environment spanning multiple platforms, this paper proposes a decision support framework with the blackboard model to integrate all complementary features into a single automated test environment for multi-platform client/server applications. Before testing client/server applications, the input into this framework are testing tools with different approaches and client sites which are going to run the test. The planning agent will make a decision dynamically and produce a testing plan to allocate testing tasks to these testing tools to client sites. Two complementary features for testing client/server applications are illustrated in this paper to demonstrate how the framework works. The concept of mobile agents is applied to launch the test driver to different client sites, execute the tests and bring back the test results from client sites as well as the trace file from the server site for inspecting the interaction behavior among clients. Based on the multicast framework, the same test data can be broadcasted to multiple clients sites to run the tests simultaneously and the test results can be returned from client sites for examining the problem of repeated executions.

Keywords: Blackboard Model; Automated Test Execution; Mobile Agents; Chat System.

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1. Introduction

Education has an important role in improving the quality of human resource and develop Indonesian nation for manifest welfare and educate life nation refer to "Mukadimah" on 1945 Constitution fourth alinea.

Baharuddin and Esa [1] stated that *Proses belajar adalah serangkaian aktivitas yang terjadi pada pusat saraf individu yang belajar.*

Learning process is activities that occurred in individuals' nerve study. Skinner [5] stated that the study is something adaptation or breakdown Act behavior that lasts in a manner progressive.

In learning process, the teacher has an important role as teachers and students as an object study, the teacher has the right using various teaching models to achieve the aims of learning process and it will ease achieved if students have a good motivation in learning. The teacher role is needed to motivate students learn. It is refer to teacher role namely a student motivator.

Teaching learning process is an educate activities. The value of educate covering the interactions between teacher and students. It is namely the value of educate interactions because the teaching learning process to achieve the aims of learning process which patterned teaching learning process before. The teacher awareness in teaching learning plan is systematically support in teaching needed [6].

Learning motivation is internal and external encouragement on students who learning the behavioral transform which having some of indicators supported in common. Those are influenced succeed in learning [2]. Motivation determines the level of success or failure of student learning activities. Learning without motivation is difficult to succeed, in essays.

Low or lack of motivation to learn in the history subjects of class XI IPS in Bandar Lampung SMA 6 is influenced by the conventional learning process and is still teacher-centered, making students less active and less motivated in the classroom learning process, subject teachers History tells students not to pay attention to the teacher when explaining the material, not focusing, and if given the opportunity to ask questions about the material explained the students seemed not eager to ask questions, or instead the teacher asked questions most students chose to be quiet so that learning was less active and efficient and influential on low student learning outcomes.

The learning process can run well if the set learning objectives can be achieved optimally. Improving the quality of student learning processes and results needs to be pursued in order to obtain good quality education. To achieve this, it is necessary to get attention, and handling both from the government, family, and from the student's own business. Learning outcomes are changes in student behavior due to learning.
[4].

Motivation should be seen as a very important factor in the learning process. The motivated student has strength to learn, to discover and capitalize on capabilities, to improve academic performance and adapt to the demands of the school context. Psychology, membership motivation and learning success.

So, with this study, we intend to examine how perceived sense of school belonging and intrinsic motivation influences. A structural model reveals that the negative sense of belonging has a negative impact on intrinsic motivation and on perceived learning. In turn, intrinsic motivation is positive and significantly influences are perceived learning in the course motivation is positively and significantly influences the perceived learning in the course [3]. Based on the description described above, this problem is important to be examined and proven to determine the effect of the inquiry learning model and learning motivation on the learning outcomes of history in Bandar Lampung Public High School 6. The teacher needs an alternative learning model that is appropriate and innovative to condition learning history and motivate students to be

more motivated to focus on learning using the Inquiry Learning Model. This inquiry learning model is an educational interaction whose purpose is to foster self-confidence and activate student motivation to be able to support and help one another so that eventually the results of historical learning will increase.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses an experimental method with desaintreatment by level 2 x 2. Variables in this study consisted of two independent variables namely inquiry learning model (X1) and learning motivation (X2) as independent variables. bound (dependent variable) is the Learning Outcomes of students (Y). This study is a type of experimental research using one control class with conventional learning models and one experimental class with Inquiry learning models.

The population in this study were students of class XI IPS Bandar Lampung High School 6. While the sample in the study was carried out by random sampling technique which would later be obtained by one control class and one experimental class. The sample consisted of XI IPS 1 class, which amounted to 28 students and XI IPS 2 class, totaling 28 students. The number of students who were the subjects of the study were 56 students. Before being given treatment, questionnaires were distributed to determine learning motivation. The questionnaire filling score is arranged based on the highest score to the lowest score.

3. Results and Discussions

Results test hypothesis first to show results from calculation results calculation Analysis Variance (ANOVA) Two-Lane obtained F count data for learning models have a score of 14,349, with score F_{table} 4.15 on the level, in fact, $\alpha = 0.05$. So that could be proven that value $F_{count} > F_{table}$ the meaning that is there is difference results learn the history between students were given the treatment of learning models Inquiry compared with students were given the treatment of learning models Conventional. Based on average yield learn history groups that use learning models Inquiry (A1) has to score of 27.88, whereas groups that use learning models Conventional (A2) has a score of 24.31, proven that the average group A1 is higher from group A2 or $\mu_{A1} > \mu_{A2}$. Then the test hypothesis first proves that H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. The second hypothesis, there is the influence of interaction between the use of learning models and student learning motivation. The ANOVA calculation results show that the interaction has a score of $F_{count} = 62.541$ with a score of $F_{table} = 4.20$ at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$, so there is an interaction between the use of learning models and Motivation Learning towards students' historical learning outcomes.

Hypothesis third, the average value of historical learning outcomes in students who have high learning motivation and use inquiry learning models (A1B1) which is 32,88 while those using the Conventional learning model (A2B1) are 21.88. Comparison of the average value as a continuation of the proven interaction between the learning model applied and Learning Motivation, then testing the third hypothesis followed by the Tuckey Test to test the significance level. These results indicate that the Q_{value} is calculated greater than Q_{table} at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$, it can be concluded that there are significant differences between the average historical learning outcomes in students who have high Learning Motivation who use the Inquiry learning model

(A1B1) with those using Conventional learning models (A2B1). So that it can be proven also that the average A1B1 is greater than A2B1, so the third hypothesis can be proved that is H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. Hypothesis fourth, the average value of historical learning outcomes in students who have low learning motivation and use inquiry learning models (A1B2) which is 22,88 while those using Conventional learning models (A2B2) which is 26.75. Comparison of the average value as a continuation of the proven interaction between the learning model applied and Learning Motivation, then testing the third hypothesis followed by *the Tuckey Test* to test the significance level. These results indicate that the Q_{value} is greater than Q_{table} at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$, it can be concluded that there are significant differences between the average historical learning outcomes in students who have Learning Motivation low and use Inquiry learning models (A1B2) with those using Conventional learning models (A2B2). So that it can be proven also that the average A1B2 is lower than the average A2B2, so the fourth hypothesis can be proved that is H_1 accepted and H_0 rejected.

Based on the hypothesis testing, the results show that there is a significant influence, which is given the Inquiry learning model of students' historical learning outcomes. So that inquiry learning can be considered more capable of optimizing historical learning outcomes, compared with students who use conventional learning models. The application of inquiry learning models seems to be better used because in addition to being able to actively involve students that make students motivated to learn, also students to build understanding of information and formulate their own knowledge of the topic of material they are studying.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the research described and discussed earlier, it can be concluded that the results of research that has been obtained indicate that: (1) Inquiry learning model has a significant influence on students' historical learning outcomes, this is indicated by learning outcomes in groups of students given treatment Inquiry learning models are higher than historical learning outcomes in groups of students given treatment in the form of conventional learning models.(2) The interaction between the learning model and learning motivation can be seen from the relationship between the learning model applied and the level of learning motivation towards students' historical learning outcomes. Effect of the application of inquiry learning models. (3) in students who have high learning motivation abilities proved positive for students' historical learning outcomes, because the historical learning outcomes are higher than the historical learning outcomes of students who have high learning motivation given the treatment of conventional learning models. (4)The influence of the application of conventional learning models on students who have low learning motivation is also proven positive for students' historical learning outcomes, because the historical learning outcomes are higher than the historical learning outcomes of students who have low learning motivation given the treatment of inquiry learning models.

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